

COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES OF THE HOLLOW GLASS MICROSPHERE FILLED RESIN-MATRIX COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Keywords: Composite materials, Hollow glass microsphere, Mechanical properties, Syntactic foam

ABSTRACT

This work was focused on the synthesis and mechanical properties of hollow glass microsphere filled resin-matrix composites, which were widely applied in deep-sea fields. The density, compressive properties of hollow glass microsphere (HGM) filled resin composites were investigated in the present paper, the volume fraction of hollow glass microsphere was varied from 35 to 50 vol.%. The results showed that the density, compressive strength and modulus of the composites decreased simultaneously with increasing HGM content, which indicates that the properties of the composites are mainly dependent on the characteristics of hollow glass microsphere. The results indicated mechanical properties of resin-matrix composites could be modified by changing the HGM weight fraction, this discover would make it become a promising engineering material in the related fields.

1 INTRODUCTION

Syntactic foams are made of filler materials dispersed in various reinforcement, and have been used as structural components [1-3]. Hollow glass microsphere (HGM) consists of inner inert gas and outer stiff glass, which makes it having a low density but high compression strength. Syntactic foam consisting of HGM filled polymeric matrix is technologically interesting and hence extensively investigated recently [4-5]. This kind of composite material has been considered as excellent structural material since it has exhibited isotropic physical properties, high specific compressive strength and stiffness, low moisture absorption, high damage tolerance, and well-designed [6]. It can be used as aero space, maritime industries, the production of sandwich composite core elements, etc. [4, 7].

Syntactic foams properties have been extensively studied. The mechanical properties such as stiffness and fracture toughness of syntactic foams have been observed [8-10]. Syntactic foams filling with the various microspheres weight fraction have been processed [11]. Several analytical studies for compressive failure of the syntactic foams have been made. Kim and Oh have been reported that failure mode of syntactic foams with relatively high-density foams under compression failed by the formation of 45° shear planes [12]. Ho Sung Kim found that failure of syntactic foams had two different failure modes, one was characterized by longitudinal splitting and the other was by layered crushing [3]. The former occurred at a low density of foam and the latter occurred at relatively high densities of foam. Considering the applications of syntactic foams, the study of failure properties of these materials is urgently needed. It is important to understand failure mechanisms of syntactic foam prior to development of syntactic foams to the needs of structural component design.

In this paper, the effects of HGM weight fraction (35 – 50 wt%) on the density and compressive properties of HGM filled resin-matrix composites were systematically investigated. The results will guide the application of HGM filled resin composite, especially in buoyancy industry.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Constituent materials

Vinyl ester resin (Tianhe resin Co., Ltd.) was selected as the matrix material, and methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP, Tianhe resin Co., Ltd.) was used as catalyst. The content of catalyst in matrix resin was 2 wt%. The hollow glass microspheres (trade name: S38/HS, 3M China Ltd) were used as fillers.

2.2 Synthesis of composite materials

The Vinyl ester resin–HGM composites were synthesized by mechanical mixing measurement. The composites were fabricated according to the following steps: (i) the resin and the catalyst with the designed amount were carefully mixed in a beaker by manual stirring; (ii) then, the microspheres with the designed weight fraction were slowly added to the resin mixture, the weight fraction of HGM in composite was designed as 35%–50%; (iii) the mixtures were stirred by a high-speed mixing machine (Rose, A300). The stirring speed must be carefully controlled to avoid the breakage of microspheres, since the microspheres tended to float on top due to their lower density compared to the resin. More stirring time was needed for lower weight fraction of hollow microspheres to ensure a uniform distribution; (iv) the mixture was then transferred to a stainless steel mold which was smeared with mold releasing agent, and pump degassed in a vacuum drying oven at about 60 °C until few bubbles appeared on the surface; (v) finally, the mixture was cured at 40 °C for 8 h to complete the polymerization.

2.3 Characterization

The densities were measured according to ISO 845. The samples were cut into 10×10×10 mm of nominal dimensions. For each designed constituent proportion of the composite, at least five specimens were prepared and measured [13].

Compression test was carried out according to the procedures outlined in ASTM D1621-04 standard by using Instron 4469 test systems, the dimension of the specimens used for compression test was 30×30×30 mm, and the constant deformation rate carried out in compression test was 1 mm/min. For each designed constituent proportion of the composite, at least five specimens were prepared and measured.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Density of composite

The density of the composite material varied significantly as the content of HGM filled in matrix was changed for the reason that the density of HGM was lower than that of the matrix resin. Fig.1 displays the effect of the weight fraction of hollow glass microspheres on the density of the composite. It indicated that the density of the composite decreased with the increase of HGM content. When the HGM content increased from 35 wt% to 50 wt%, the density of the composite decreased from 0.64 g/cm³ to 0.49 g/cm³, the decrease rate was approximate 23.4%. The reason of the density of composites being decreased compared to the expected values lied in that the HGM density was lower than that of the resin, thus as the HGM content increased, the density of composites became more close to that of the HGM.

Fig. 1 The density of different weight fractions of HGM

3.2 Compressive properties

Typical compressive stress-strain curves for vinyl ester/HGM composites with four different contents of HGM are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Compressive stress- strain curves of syntactic foam with different weight fractions of HGM

These curves are qualitatively similar to those observed for adhesively bonded syntactic foams [14]. It indicated that each curve included two stages, which were the initial high slope and the followed negative slope. The initial high slope was caused by the elastic deformation of the composites and the low slope/plateau regime should be related to crushing/densification of microspheres (see crushing/densification mechanism below) [15, 16].

Fig.3 (a) and Fig.3 (b) show the plot of the compressive strength and the compressive modulus versus the content of HGM respectively. The compressive modulus was calculated based on the measured stress–strain data of the initial linear region in Fig.2. The results indicated that the compressive modulus and strength of the composites decreased as the weight fraction of the HGM increased, the reason lied in that the rigidity of HGM was higher than that of the resin matrix. As the weight fraction of the HGM increased, the compression failure of the composite became closer to that of the HGM and the compression yield strain became lower. As the weight fraction of the HGM decreased, the compression failure of the composite became more close to that of the resin matrix and the compression yield strain became higher. When the HGM content was 35 wt%, the compressive strength and modulus of the composite were 64.9 MPa and 2.37 GPa, respectively. With the HGM content increased to 50 wt%, the compressive strength and modulus of the composite decreased to 32.5 MPa and 1.98 GPa, respectively.

Fig. 3 The compressive strength and modulus of composites as a function of HGM weight fraction

Fig.4 Comparison of specific compressive modulus of vinyl ester matrix syntactic foams with neat vinyl ester resin

The specific compressive strength of the composites was shown in Fig. 4. It indicated that the maximum specific compression strength of the composite was 104.21 KPa•m³/kg with the HGM content being 40 wt%. Compared with other composites with different HGM content it had a low density and relatively high compression strength, and thus the combination property of compression strength and density was the best. Because the combination of HGM and resin matrix was optimal when the HGM content was 40 wt%, under the action of shear stress, shear failures occurred in HGM and the fractures absorbed more energy, thus the composite had a high strength. Moreover, the expansion of the shear cracks was hampered by the HGM, resulted in the stress being scattered.

4 CONCLUSION

The concentration of filled HGM increased from 35 wt% to 50 wt%, and the density of the composite decreased as much as 23.4% from 0.64g / cm³ to 0.49 g/cm³. By studying the four composites compression performance, it was concluded that the increasing HGM content in glass micro-spheres will lead the declining of compressive properties of some materials. This is because materials with different contents of HGMs will exhibit different forms during compression damage. By comparison with the compressive strength of different materials, we could easily find that when the content of the HGM was 40 wt%, the material has a maximum compression strength, that is 104.21 KPa•m³/kg. Meanwhile, the materials also show the best compressive strength and overall density.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express thanks to the financial support from Natural Science Foundation of China (51479037). The authors have attempted to include all available studies and omission of any reference is unintentional.

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